

MARKETING OF SOCIAL NETWORKS IN THE MODERN WORLD ROLE IN THE FIELD

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Annotation: social in the modern world in this scientific article the role of networks in marketing has been studied. Also social to what extent enterprises use their brands among consumers with the help of networks proposals and recommendations have been made in the dam of the possibility that they will achieve widespread distribution.

Keywords: Marketing, Brand, blog, consumer, advertising, SMM, strategy, marketer, social media.

Marketing business owners to interact with consumers it is an important tool that can be used. From past to present businesses are traditional media for their marketing relationships they made extensive use of tools and traditional media tools. However, today's social network and Social thanks to the development of technology and the internet in the day media tools have become more prominent in marketing communications. Social networks have many advantages over traditional media and

has positive properties. Therefore, marketing Communications today activities are moving from traditional to social networks. Both business owners and consumers are increasingly using social media every day. Communication and interaction

between enterprises and consumers in social networks the intensification began to advance social media marketing.

Social media marketing strategies help businesses brand recognition gives. However, entrepreneurs are best for use in modern technologies creativity and innovation of the strategy because they do not know the tools they did not always fully use their capabilities. It is worth noting that some organizations also do not recognize the benefits of social media. Internet many opened up opportunities, such as podcasts, blogs and advertising such as social media online that uses its mechanisms to reach its target audience is a marketing weapon. As well as the internet, interacting with users and allows you to create communities, which allows you to share and discuss knowledge facilitates. Examples of popular social networks are YouTube, Facebook and Twitter can be made. Businesses have a high level of social media marketing have developed several strategies to ensure availability. Marketers which uses to advertise their products on social networks one of the strategies is that celebrities recline these products [1]. This Facebook Instagram, Tiktok, Tiktok, advertising is carried out through social media sites etc. These celebrities are considered to have high social significance, hence for they attract more customers to the products [2]. Famous people, they are considered a powerful intermediary for advertising in marketing because they are it can easily grab the attention of buyers and make the brand name known appeal to more people than other traditional advertising methods make, and have the opportunity to enhance the reputation of the brand [3]. Currently entrepreneurs and organizations, have many observers on social networks application for personal account holders to advertise their products it is natural to do. According to Arca, 2012, social media marketing, to businesses achieve the intended traffic, create leaders, get an understanding of the market and improving competitors, public relations and human resources, cost savings and customer feedback, brand impact and was instrumental in increasing its popularity [4]. Social network marketing consumers i.e. in the personal interests and sites of network users it will help to attract the buyer based on the feedback left. This in the way, companies are most interested in what they offer they will have the

opportunity to appeal to people [5]. Social media an additional advantage of marketing is its ability to provide, that is, to customers enterprises that have the opportunity to offer customized products is able to provide consumers [5].

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